

华北电力大学

NORTH CHINA ELECTRIC POWER UNIVERSITY

GREEN ENERGY INNOVATION

Project Title:

**Transitioning to Green Energy Housing
in Bangladesh – (Drivers and Barriers)**

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Outline of project

Project Summary

This project is aimed to study the key driving elements and barriers that effect the process of transitioning to Green Energy Housing. The project will look to identify the major factors that influence this transition process and how best to overcome the barriers in order to get positive results.

Project Objectives

- Identify key Driving factors that influence the transition into Green Housing
- Identify the major barriers and seek solutions on how to overcome them.
- Investigate possible future barriers that would affect this transition decision process.

Significance.

Sustainable housing is more than just an environmental benefit, it also benefits the social, environmental, and economic pillars of sustainability. It is for this reason that green buildings have been considered as key solutions for reducing GHG emissions and the negative effects they bring about. Achieving this in the buildings sector is a challenging but attainable goal. This project aims at looking into the solutions to reach this goal through assessing the key factors that influence the process.

Chapter 1: Introduction

Green energy is any energy type that is generated from natural resources, such as sunlight, wind or water. It often comes from renewable energy sources although there are some differences between renewable and green energy. The key with these energy resources is that they don't harm the environment through factors such as releasing greenhouse gases into the atmosphere.

In order to be deemed green energy, a resource cannot produce pollution, such as is found with fossil fuels. This means that not all sources used by the renewable energy industry are green. For example, power generation that burns organic material from sustainable forests may be renewable, but it is not necessarily green, due to the CO₂ produced by the burning process itself. Green energy sources are usually naturally replenished, as opposed to fossil fuel sources like natural gas or coal, which can take millions of years to develop. Green sources also often avoid mining or drilling operations that can be damaging to eco-systems. Green energy has the capacity to replace fossil fuels in the future; however, it may require varied production from different means to achieve this. Geothermal, for example, is particularly effective in places where this resource is easy to tap into, while wind energy or solar power may be better suited to other geographic locations.

However, by bringing together multiple green energy sources to meet our needs, and with the advancements that are being made with regards to production and development of these resources, there is every reason to believe that fossil fuels could be phased out. We are still some years away from this happening, but the fact remains that this is necessary to reduce climate change, improve the environment and move to a more sustainable future.

A green home is a type of house designed to be environmentally sustainable. Green homes focus on the efficient use of "energy, water, and building materials". A green home may use sustainably sourced, environmentally friendly, or recycled building materials. It may include sustainable energy sources such as solar or geothermal, and be sited to take maximum advantage of natural features such as sunlight and tree cover to improve energy efficiency.

In the United States, the green building movement began in the 1970s, after the price of oil began to increase sharply. In response, researchers began to look into more energy efficient systems. Many organizations were founded in the 1990s to promote green buildings. Some organizations worked to improve consumer knowledge so that they could have more green homes. The International Code Council and the National Association of Home Builders began working in 2006 to create a "voluntary green home building standard".

Zero Energy Homes are the Ultimate Energy Efficient Homes. Zero energy homes are just like any home—except better. They are regular grid-tied homes that are so air-tight, well insulated, and energy efficient that they produce as much renewable energy as they consume over the course of a year, leaving the occupants with a net zero energy bill, and a carbon-free home.

Figure 1.

A zero-energy home is not just a “green home” or a home with solar panels. A zero-energy home combines advanced design and superior building systems with energy efficiency and on-site solar panels to produce a better home. Zero energy homes are ultra-comfortable, healthy, quiet, sustainable homes that are affordable to live in.

Chapter 2: Overview of Green Housing Transition in Bangladesh

Bangladesh contains around 28% urban area of the total population which is approximately 41.5 million people who are living in urban areas of Bangladesh and is expected 1.5 times current level to reach 63 million by 2.8% mean population growth rate in 2025. Between 2016 and 2020, it was found that housing the deficit raised from 1.13 to 4.6 million units for 2001 to 2010 in urban areas. Consequently, buildings have 40% share in the energy consumption of Bangladesh resulting from the alarming rate urbanization and rapid energy demand. The Nationally Determined Contribution of Bangladesh focusing on climate commitments aims to moderate overall energy consumption in

commercial buildings at 25%). Although construction sector especially the building construction is increasing remarkably, green buildings have not been yet constructed increasingly.

Bangladesh’s renewable energy journey has been quite slow. The country has implemented energy policy incentives in the direction of the disposition of renewables and turned away from coal imports. At the same time, planning to develop domestic coal production and increase its reliance on LNG as a transitional fuel.

Multidimensional challenges are hindering the proliferation of green buildings in Bangladesh

The green building market is perceived to have immense potential in Bangladesh but requires a highly conducive ecosystem to help realise the potential. The adjacent exhibit demonstrates positioning of the green building landscape in the country with respect to five major facilitating pillars.

Research on green building from the perspective of climate change remain scarce in the context of Bangladesh. Urbanization and development are increasing day by day and it is important to understand the different issues related to green building, for example, the present condition of governance aspects, challenges, and recommendations to further develop the green building practices in Bangladesh. This study will improve the knowledge in this regard.

Chapter 3: World Overview of Green Housing Transition

Green energy clusters, or cleantech clusters, are increasingly pursued by localities around the world seeking to establish sustainable energy economies. Sustainable energy cluster initiatives aim to stimulate local and regional economic development by creating the conditions that attract and promote innovative firms in the area of sustainable, renewables-based energy. Firms engaged in the development and implementation of renewable energy technologies, smart grid technologies, and low-impact transportation systems are particularly sought, as these sectors are seen as high growth sectors with potential to both address critical sustainability challenges and solidify and advance a region's knowledge-based economy. It is expected that these firms will benefit from the same agglomeration economies that have long benefited firms in other clustering industries, and that these firm-based activities will generate economic spillovers that will promote dynamism in a local green economy. The 'green' cluster strategy is rapidly emerging as a regional development and sustainability planning approach worldwide. Examples are found in large 'greenfield' development projects, such as Masdar City, United Arab Emirates, and several emerging Chinese eco-cities. Sustainable development has become the center of recent national policies, strategies and development plans of many countries.

Transition in North America

In Canada, Mexico, and the United States, commercial and residential building operations account for about 20, 30, and 40 percent of the primary energy consumption, respectively. They typically also account for 20 to 25 percent of the landfill waste and 5 to 12 percent of the water consumption. The United States Green Building Council estimates that green building, on average, currently reduces energy use by 30 percent, carbon emissions by 35 percent, water use by 30 to 50 percent, and generates waste cost savings of 50 to 90 percent.

Substantial research supports the health and productivity benefits of green features, such as daylighting, increased natural air ventilation and moisture reduction, and the use of low-emitting floor carpets, glues, paints and other interior finishes and furnishings. In the United States, the annual cost of building-related sickness is estimated to be at \$58 billion. According to researchers, green building has the potential to generate an additional \$200 billion annually in the United States in worker performance by creating offices with improved indoor air quality.

Buildings also affect our quality of life, infrastructure development, and transportation systems. Beyond individual buildings, poor site development often leads to inefficient land use, resulting in greater energy consumption and travel time, loss of productivity, polluted runoff to surface water and wastewater treatment systems, loss of agricultural lands, fragmented habitats, and fiscal stress to local communities.

Buildings and Climate Change

Reports from leading scientists throughout the world underline the need for urgent action on climate change. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) projects that without more immediate action to limit greenhouse gas emissions, global warming could cause irreversible and possibly catastrophic consequences.

Every year, the energy used by buildings in North America causes more than 2,200 megatons of CO₂ to be released into the atmosphere, about 35 percent of the continent's total. Recent studies by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), McKinsey & Company (an international consulting firm), and Vattenfall (a Swedish utility company), indicate that improved building practices are some of the quickest and cheapest ways to reduce significantly greenhouse gas emissions, often with net economic benefit. An increasing number of organizations, institutions, and government entities in North America are calling for aggressive energy performance improvements in the building sector. In short, green building represents some of the ripest "low-hanging fruit" for achieving significant reductions in climate change emissions.

A background study commissioned by the CEC Secretariat as part of this study signals the tremendous possibilities in terms of energy improvements and greenhouse gas emissions reductions in the building sector by 2030 and suggests a path forward toward zero net-energy and carbon-neutral buildings. A rapidly increasing market uptake of currently available and emerging advanced energy-saving technologies could result in annual reductions of 1711 megatonnes (MT) of CO₂ into the atmosphere in North America by 2030, compared to a business-as-usual approach. This is nearly equivalent to the 1756 MT of CO₂ emissions from the transportation sector in the United States in 2000. With these dramatic reductions in energy requirements, renewable energy could provide additional energy needs, making the widespread adoption of zero net-energy and carbon-neutral buildings possible.

In the United States and Canada, many efforts are currently underway to accelerate the market uptake of green building. Economics are helping to drive these changes. Studies show that the cost premium to deliver sustainable properties to the market has declined considerably in recent years, and that experienced teams are delivering them at costs competitive with conventional buildings. There is, however, a cost to organizations to gain the experience necessary to achieve this. In addition, studies show that the significant life-cycle financial benefits of green design more than make up for the additional initial cost associated with green building. Unfortunately, in many cases, due to policy, ownership, and business structures, the benefits of green building do not accrue to those making the investment. Research presented in the background papers to this report shows how governments at all levels are working to address these and other obstacles to influence the uptake of green building through the integrated use of building codes; zoning regulations; tax-based incentives; and preferential treatment for green developers (such as fast-track permitting). In addition, green building practices are also being spurred by demand offset programs (in which

a developer reduces energy and water demand as a condition of permitting); preferred purchasing; tax shifting; and government-supported research, development, and educational programs.

Mexico has a tradition of architecture that favors environmentally sensitive, small-footprint building practices and designs. Policy efforts to promote green building are relatively new and generally focused on the housing sector. The country's National Housing Commission (Comisión Nacional de Vivienda—Conavi) is documenting green practices and working to define criteria for green homes. Infonavit, a large housing fund in Mexico supported by mandatory employer and employee contributions, has created a "green mortgage" program.

The Comisión Nacional para el Ahorro de Energía (National Commission for Energy Efficiency—Conae) recently began work to implement a solar water heater program. This initiative, along with green procurement guidelines, leasing and public sector services, is sure to play a part in the process. Also, new hotels in some environmentally sensitive areas are integrating technology to reduce their environmental footprint and a number of private corporations are designing their headquarters to be more environmentally efficient.

Current market forces and government programs alone, however, will not drive the necessary changes in the building industry. Key barriers to a market transformation in North America include: the predominant practice by governments and institutions of separating capital and operating budgets instead of using life-cycle budgeting; the split incentive problem, where the one who pays for the green features often does not realize its benefits; a tendency to rely on business-as-usual approaches in view of the perceived cost, risk, and uncertainty of green building; limited awareness and knowledge of green building; and lack of coordination and consistency in government policies affecting building.

In Mexico, additional barriers include the paucity of urban planning and building regulations that address sustainability issues, the lack of a widely-used certification system for green building practices, limited implementation of existing standards, and the lack of data on energy and water use in buildings.

Transition in Germany

Germany is generally recognised to be the pioneer in establishing energy policy for sustainable development, and it is currently the most successful country for the promotion of renewable energy towards a sustainable energy system transition. In 2011, German government announced the

Energiewende ('energy transformation') and decided to reduce the amount of fossil fuels from 80% of energy supply to 20% by 2050. The phase-out of nuclear energy, reduction of fossil fuels and dramatic increase in projected energy efficiency are the three major components of the German Energiewende.

We won't manage to fundamentally restructure Germany's energy supply overnight. The energy transition is to be gradually rolled out up to 2050. It affects all levels of government, small and large companies, and the lives of the whole population. Such a task for entire generations will only succeed if we have a clear compass, a precise roadmap and good cooperation.

The German government's Energy Concept is the compass for the energy transition. It sets clear goals for all the areas it covers - electricity, heat and transport. The focus is on two core objectives: Firstly, the energy supply should be increasingly based on renewable energy. Secondly, energy should be used more and more efficiently.

The Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy is responsible for choosing the right measures to attain the goals of the energy transition. To do this, the ministry is following a precise road map: the 10-point Energy Agenda outlines the steps that need to be taken by this government and dovetails the various fields of action in terms of substance and timing. The overview shows what we have already achieved and what tasks still lay ahead of us.

The energy transition is a joint effort. So, everyone involved in the energy transition is closely involved in the implementation. The Federal Government, the Länder and the municipalities, and also commerce and society. Ultimately, the energy transition will only succeed if everyone uses their strengths to make it happen.

The energy transition: key projects

Fostering the energy transition in the buildings sector

The building sector plays a key role to play in the implementation of the energy transition. It accounts for almost 40% of Germany's energy consumption. The government is therefore aiming to make Germany's building stock virtually climate-neutral by 2050. To achieve this, we will have to cut primary energy consumption (oil and gas) by 80%. This requires higher energy efficiency and greater use of renewable energy.

Boosting energy efficiency in buildings

New buildings are to be designed to use as little energy as possible. They will have to comply with the minimum requirements of the Energy Saving Ordinance. But many existing buildings also need to become more energy-efficient. Drafty windows and non-insulated roofs and outside walls mean that older buildings in particular consume a lot of energy. Insulating the building's

outer shell, replacing old heating units and renovating windows cuts heating costs and improves comfort.

Anyone wishing to modernise his or her home's energy performance should start by utilising the "on-the-spot advice". An energy consultant analyses the building and produces a tailored energy rehabilitation concept. The government covers up to 60% of the consultancy costs – up to a maximum of 800 euros for one-family and two-family houses, and up to 1,100 euros for multi-family houses. A further grant is available if the energy consultant's report is discussed in meetings of apartment owners or advisory boards.

When investment decisions are taken, the tried-and-trusted KfW funding programmes on energy-efficient building and modernisation can be used. Grants and low-interest loans from the KfW have helped more than 3.9 million dwellings to be refurbished or built in an energy-efficient way since 2006. The Federal Government is providing 2 billion euros for this each year. It should be noted that the standards to be met under the KfW programmes are far higher than the minimum requirements imposed by the Energy Saving Ordinance. The principle is as follows: the greater the energy efficiency achieved, the higher the financial assistance provided.

KfW programmes for energy-efficient construction and retrofitting			
For residential buildings		For municipal and social service buildings	For commercial buildings
“Energy-efficient refurbishment”	“Energy-efficient construction”	“IKK/IKU – energy-efficient construction and retrofitting” (from 1 October 2015)	“KfW Energy Efficiency Programme – Energy-efficient Construction and Retrofitting”
<p>What is being funded? Individual retrofitting measures (heating, windows, insulation) or comprehensive refurbishment to meet KfW Efficiency House standards.</p> <p>In addition, grants are provided for independent energy-related advice on planning and construction.</p> <p>How does funding work? Either: low-interest loan with additional grant towards repayment, or: grant towards investment costs (only for owners of single-family and two-family houses, owners of apartments and associations of owners of apartments)</p> <p>Further information? KfW-Infocenter: infocenter@kfw.de</p>	<p>What is being funded? New energy-efficient residential buildings which meet the standard of KfW Efficiency House 70, 55 or 40.</p> <p>How does funding work? Low-interest loan; additional grant towards repayment provided if KfW Efficiency House 55 or 40 is built</p> <p>Further information? KfW-Infocenter: infocenter@kfw.de</p>	<p>What is being funded? 1) Individual retrofitting measures (heating, windows, insulation) or comprehensive refurbishment to meet KfW Efficiency House standards. 2) New energy-efficient buildings which meet the standard of KfW Efficiency House 70 or 55.</p> <p>How does funding work? Retrofitting: low-interest loan with additional grant towards repayment New buildings: low-interest loan; additional grant towards repayment provided if KfW Efficiency House 55 is built</p> <p>Further information? KfW-Infocenter: infocenter@kfw.de</p>	<p>What is being funded? 1) Individual retrofitting measures (heating, windows, insulation) or comprehensive refurbishment to meet KfW Efficiency House standards. 2) New energy-efficient commercial buildings which meet the standard of KfW Efficiency House 70 or 55.</p> <p>How does funding work? Retrofitting: low-interest loan with additional grant towards repayment New buildings: low-interest loan; additional grant towards repayment provided if KfW Efficiency House 55 is built</p> <p>Further information? KfW-Infocenter: infocenter@kfw.de</p>
Principle: The more energy-efficient the building, the higher the assistance			

The CO2 Building Renovation Programme: KfW programmes for energy-efficient construction and retrofitting

Renewable energy is to be increasingly used not just to generate electricity, but also heat. The Renewable Energy Sources Heat Act therefore stipulates those new buildings should gain some of their heat from renewable energy sources. If owners of existing buildings switch their heating systems to renewable energy, e.g. solar-thermal installations, pellet heating or efficient heat pumps, they are eligible for financial assistance from the Market Incentive Programme (MAP), which was received in April 2015 and now offers even better support. Companies which generate the heat they need from renewable energy, or municipalities which build local heating networks to distribute heat generated from renewable energy, can also receive grants towards this from the MAP.

United Nation

The United Nations General Assembly proposed a set of global Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) which included 17 goals and 169 targets at the UN in New York by the Open Working Group. In addition, a preliminary set of 330 indicators was introduced in March 2015. The SDGs place greater value and demands on the scientific community than did the Millennium Development Goals. In addressing climate change, renewable energy, food, health and water provision requires a coordinated global monitoring and modelling of many factors which are socially, economically and environmentally oriented.

Transition in the UK

The UK has a legal obligation under EU law to generate 20% of all energy consumption from renewable energy sources by 2020, and it has a legally mandated policy goal of an 80% reduction in national climate change emissions by 2050 which was made in 2008, and to reach net-zero carbon emissions by 2050 through an amendment to the law made in 2019.

Transition in Denmark

In 2001, an expert group was formed by the Danish Energy Agency to investigate the problem of excess electricity generation arising from the high penetration of wind generation and combined heating and power plant in the Danish energy system. Denmark has a leading role in the development of wind power generation which can go back to Poul la Cour who developed and built a wind turbine for electricity production and thus initiated modern wind power development.

Transition in China

In 2017, the National Development and Reform Commission (NDRC) of China issued the 13th Five Year Plan on energy development, and this is the basic outline of China's energy policy from 2016 to 2020. The Category of electricity generation are coal, natural gas, wind power and solar power. The improvement of energy demand and energy supply structure is the pillar of the energy policy in the 13th Five Year Plan, which aims to address the problem of “placing an emphasis on facility construction, but disregarding usage” in the existing renewable energy policy.

Chapter 4: Drivers and Barriers

Investing in the renewable energy through transitioning to Green housing can help emerge as a key tool to speed up Bangladesh's net-zero commitments. Looking at global and regional economic perspectives, renewable energy is meaningfully more economical than imported fossil fuels. The expected reduction in solar module prices within the next ten years suggest that renewable energy will not only become the cheapest form of new power in Bangladesh, but it will also be speedy to construct and in line with the country's Paris Agreement targets. Renewable energy must be taken more seriously in the country.

The most beneficial economic and social benefits of Bangladesh' green buildings can be pointed out to be the issue of energy saving, closely followed by the climate change mitigation. Other significant benefits would be long term resilience, water efficiency, and the improvement in the quality of life. In spite of the initial investment being high, the operational and maintenance cost of green buildings in the long run is very low.

a. Climate change mitigation, b. Job creation, c. Income generation, d. Trade balance, e. The Efficient use of roof garden, f. Energy saving, g. Saving of medical expenses, h. Improved quality of life, i. Long term resilience, j. Water efficiency.

Economic and social aspects of green buildings benefits (2020)

However, green buildings would not be as beneficial when considering income generation, job creation, and saving on medical expenses. implementing green building practices in Bangladesh, the perception of people toward changes and as well as the lack of proper knowledge and technology, and the increased initial cost is a major barrier. The absence of regulatory authority and the necessity aspects can also be identified as being of comparatively less priority.

Policy

The Bangladesh National Building Code was established in 2006 to ensure that every building performs satisfactorily, as well as to manage and regulate development in the country. It specifies basic criteria for building design, construction, material quality, use and occupancy, placement, and maintenance in Bangladesh in order to protect life, health, property, and public welfare within reasonable bounds. After a few years, the formation of Building Construction Rules took place. After that, the green construction movement was sparked when, with the support of the International Finance Corporation, a Recommendation document for Green Building Code was published in 2012. As evidenced by the 7th Five Year Plan, which outlines the incorporation and introduction of Green Building Code considerations into the National Building Code, standardization and labeling of energy efficient electrical appliances and equipment, and the implementation of an Energy Management System for industries, Bangladesh government policies encourage green and sustainable buildings. The establishment of the Building Energy and Environment Rating for Design and Construction of Buildings (Draft) in 2018 was a big step forward in the green building arena. Bangladesh's Ministry of Housing and Public Works is also working on developing Green Buildings Guidelines.

The whole market for commercial property is expected to be US\$9.7 billion, while the total market for residential units is expected to be US\$62.6 billion. According to IFC estimates, the green building market will be valued USD 1 billion for commercial buildings and USD 2.2 billion

for residential structures by 2025. While the green market is still in its infancy, it rose significantly in 2015, thanks mostly to the industrial sector. Green building is mostly driven by the garment industry. In 2011, the country's first green building was completed. Bangladesh has 62 LEED certified activities and about 1 million LEED certified square meters as of currently (2018). The additional cost of constructing a green building is estimated to range between USD 5,800 and USD 9,500, depending on the size and scope of the project. Over a 20-year period, the financial return for green buildings is anticipated to be 4-5 times more than the additional cost of green building. The monetary benefits come from the effective use of utilities, which leads in lower energy costs, with a total predicted savings of USD 130 billion on energy bills across all industries.

Bangladesh is currently leading the globe in the addition of green factories to the economy. In Bangladesh's garment sector, there are 67 LEED certified green manufacturers and more than 280 factories enrolled for LEED certification.

Perception

All of the respondents (100%) said they were familiar with the term "climate change." The respondents' primary sources of climate change information were books and journals, as well as the internet, followed by newspapers, gatherings, and seminars. In this sense, television appeared to play a very minor role among the respondents. (Fig. 1a).

Furthermore, when asked if they believe climate change is occurring, 100% of those polled replied yes. Furthermore, when it came to determining the main causes of climate change, 52 percent of respondents believed that human activities are to blame, and that anthropogenic factors are the main driving force behind climate change, while 48 percent believed that both natural and human causes are to blame. (Supplementary Fig. 2) This demonstrates that the experts are in agreement about the effects of climate change.

Furthermore, respondents believed that growing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions were the most responsible anthropogenic factor for climate change. According to them, deforestation and fossil fuel usage closely followed GHG emissions, whereas shifting land use patterns and aerosol emissions were given less credit. (Fig. 1b).

In terms of understanding the term "green building," 100 percent of those polled knew what it meant (Table 6). They agreed that green building can assist to mitigate climate change and can also be used as a climate change adaptation technique. The majority of respondents (95 percent) agreed that wastes and emissions from domestic chores could nonetheless harm the environment near green buildings. The cost-effectiveness of green buildings, on the other hand, was a point of contention. The majority of respondents (67 percent) agreed that green buildings can be cost-effective, however 33 percent disagreed and expressed their dissatisfaction. Green building is now being addressed in the country's construction sector, according to 95% of respondents.

Design and Construction

When it comes to the design and construction of green buildings in Bangladesh, the respondents believe that environmental-friendly design and construction, as well as the sub-indicator of long-term resource efficiency, should be prioritized. This should be done in connection with biodiversity and ecological protection, as well as health and comfort. The respondents, on the other hand, believed that the maintenance of social and cultural values was less important (Fig. 3a).

Furthermore, when it comes to making buildings more energy-efficient, the respondents said that the highest importance should be given to designing buildings in an energy-efficient manner, since energy conservation is one of the most essential parts of Green Building. Increased usage of renewable energy, as well as the use of energy-efficient electric fixtures, are also deemed critical. The respondents did not place a high premium on being aware of how to use IT accessories. Respondents cited rainwater collection and efficient workplace energy control as crucial indicators. (See Fig. 3b.)

Furthermore, the respondents stated that the practice of Green Building is increasingly being addressed in the country's building sector. Only 5% of respondents, however, believe that 100–75 percent of the relevant green building sub-indicators are now being addressed in the construction industries. (Supplementary Fig. 3). Increased usage of renewable energy, as well as the use of energy-efficient electric fixtures, are also deemed critical. The respondents did not place a high premium on being aware of how to use IT accessories. Respondents cited rainwater collection and efficient workplace energy control as crucial indicators. (See Fig. 3b.)

Furthermore, the respondents stated that the practice of Green Building is increasingly being addressed in the country's building sector. Only 5% of respondents, however, believe that 100–75 percent of the relevant green building sub-indicators are now being addressed in the construction industries. Low-carbon urban development is a hot topic in the government these days, and it has been prioritized in policies. From 2012 to 2021, the Bangladesh government aimed to reduce carbon emissions by 5% unconditionally and 15% conditionally. The SREDA, which is part of the Ministry of Power, Energy, and Mineral Resources, aims to ensure energy security through utilizing renewable energy sources and improving energy efficiency (GOB, 2011). Both of these difficulties are effectively addressed by a green building. Efficient design, the use of renewable energy, CFC-free air conditioners, low UV glass, water conservation through efficient appliances,

building automation, and other measures will result in lower energy consumption and emissions. (Source: Interview).

In addition, effective planning and design, such as site selection and the use of environmentally friendly materials, protect the ecology and ecosystem, thereby reducing the negative effects of climate change. Additionally, rooftop and window gardening can aid in this aspect by sequestering additional CO₂. Enough green space is being left in government buildings, and all of the spaces can be used for planting plants, water recycling, and other activities that will ensure energy-efficient management. (Source: Interview).

a. Environment friendly design and construction, d. Protection of the biodiversity and ecosystems, c. Long term resource efficiency, d. Protection of health and comfort, e. Preservation of social and cultural values.

a. Increased use of renewable energy, b. Designing the building in an energy efficient way, c. Efficient office energy control, d. Awareness in using IT accessories, e. Rain water harvesting, f. Optimum use of air-conditioning, g. Use of energy efficient electric fixtures

Chapter 5 Solutions

Management

It would be impossible to thoroughly analyze and monitor the energy reduction program's success without credible data to measure savings. To this purpose, measuring and validating the electric and thermal savings associated with all energy operations is crucial for tracking progress and reducing costs toward a greener environment. The Inventory program built a robust procedure for fostering a greener environment at the community level. We will design a thorough measurement and verification process at the project and building levels to facilitate the examination and assessment of energy performance of specific operations. This data will be used to assess the effectiveness of specific programs, confirm predicted costs and savings, and track progress over time. The Datahub can be used to store and analyze this information.

Clearly, there are three key areas that must be strengthened in order for the green construction market to reach its full potential.

- a) The government is the one who creates policy incentives. It is now also critical to create awareness of the long-term benefits of green buildings among project developers. To attract investors, developers, and owners/tenants, additional tools such as public housing, green building, rent certification, and bonus density should be investigated.
- b) The necessity of Green Construction principles, or the implementation of such concerns into the building code, is critical. It can be supplemented by a long-term strategy of optional certifications for all new constructions, which can provide developers with a branding-based incentive to pursue.
- c) Climate-smart investment, including in green buildings to provide access to low-cost, long-term funding, plays a significant influence, as seen by the gaps. In order to promote increased green building development in Bangladesh, access to finance will need to be greatly facilitated in the future.

Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) is a method for integrating experts' or respondents' pragmatic and subjective perceptions in order to finalize or understand a decision-making procedure or its effects by examining numerous elements, such as identifying and weighting different criteria. Due to the widespread application of AHP in decision making based on expert opinions, AHP method has been used in this research. AHP has been used in green building-related works, as well as different risk assessment relates studies around the world.

According to Md. Arif Chowdhury s study on Green building aspects in Bangladesh: A study based on experts opinion regarding climate change. The following results where obtained.

Figure 5-1. challenges to implement green building and (b) suggested recommendations to recover these challenges in Bangladesh

A significant stride in the green building space was formulation of the Building Energy & Environment Rating for Design and Construction of Buildings (Draft) in 2018. Further, Bangladesh’s Ministry of Housing and Public Works is currently creating Green Buildings Guidelines. Stakeholders are banding together just to position Bangladesh as a global leader in green manufacturing and to learn from international best practices.

Table 5-1. Roles of stakeholders in green energy efficiency

Stakeholder	Key roles
Architects and consultants	Innovative designs
Code development agencies	Code compliance and technical due diligence Code development
Financial institutions	Awareness programs, market development Financial products: Targeted investments in green buildings Discount in insurance premiums
Government organizations	Regulations with strong compliance mechanisms Capacity building and job creation
Owners and occupants	Property and sales tax incentives Take responsibility of built environment Demand for sustainable and efficient buildings

Real estate developers	Adaptation to market needs
	Skills development
Technology providers	Innovation and localization of state of art technologies
	Train people in technology service operation

Management Plan for Energy

We can create annual plans to reduce energy use by using various tactics. According to multiple projections, rapidly rising countries like China will account for the majority of the increase in energy uses over the next 50 years due to growing populations. This hope lies at the heart of the China Energy and Climate Project (CECP), which was launched in the fall of 2011 and brings together academics from MIT and China to trickle the energy problem.

The CECP will bring together scholars of Joint Program on the Science and Policy of Global Change for Energy, Environment, and Economy in Beijing, China, for close collaboration and people exchange. The CECP's mission is to examine the impact of China's current and prospective energy and climate policies on technology, energy use, the environment, and economic well-being by using—and, when necessary, developing—quantitative and qualitative analysis tools. China's national and regional energy-economic models will be included in the development and deployment of such new instruments. These new tools will be informed by three primary components, which are based on the Joint Program's Emissions Prediction and Policy Analysis (EPPA) model: To better understand supply and demand in energy-intensive industries, researchers will first look at the behaviors and patterns that drive micro-level decisions made by people and businesses. Second, to estimate China's technological potential, the researchers will examine specific technology prospects such as electric vehicles, sophisticated fuels, and alternative energy sources. Finally, the environmental and economic consequences of China's present and proposed climate and energy policies will be assessed. These assessments will be carried out primarily through the use of the project's models, which are based on comparable methodologies used in the Joint Program over the last 20 years.

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